

Studies on effect of B-Site substitution on LSCF perovskite ceramics for membrane applications

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Abstract

Cobalt based perovskite oxides are advantageous for membranes applications since cobalt is beneficial for the activation of the oxygen molecules. However the reduction behavior of cobalt at high temperature leads to a structure transition which in turn results in decrease of oxygen ion transport through the membranes [1, 2]. The present work focuses to study the effect of B-Site substitutions on the perovskite system $(La,Sr)(Fe,B)O_{3-\delta}$ ($B = Zn, Co, Al$) and to develop the cobalt free perovskite for membrane applications. The perovskite MIEC oxide has been prepared using solution combustion technique. It is observed that the structural parameters like lattice parameter, tolerance factor, saddle point radius, average metal oxygen bond energy, free lattice volume were increased with decrease in the ionic radius of B-site cation. The temperature dependent electrical conduction behavior of the samples showed small polaron hopping mechanism at low temperature and metallic conductivity behavior at high temperature. It has been observed that the time constant for the electrical conductivity relaxation is more in case of Al substituted samples which might be due to the presence of high ionic conductivity compared to the Zn substituted samples. Further this electrical conduction study is correlated with the microstructure of the samples.

Keywords: LSCF, electrical properties, microstructure.

References

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